

Thermodynamic Study of Complexation of Some Transition Metal Ions with 2-Substituted Thiazolidine-4-Carboxylic Acids in Aqueous Medium**

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Potentiometric titration technique has been applied to study the complex equilibria of 2-propyl thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid, 2-phenyl thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid and 2(2')-furyl thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid with Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) at different ionic strengths and temperatures. Thermodynamic functions (ΔG° , ΔH° , ΔS°), electrostatic and cratic components have been determined. The effect of dielectric constant on stabilities is discussed.

THIAZOLIDINE compounds resemble a portion of penicillin molecule and have various biological and medicinal importance^{1,2}. Wiess *et al*³ studied complex stability constants of penicillin and a few structural analogues including 5,5-dimethyl thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acids with Cu²⁺ and concluded that 5,5-dimethyl thiazolidine carboxylic acid had the same stability values as those of penicillin. However, no attempt has been made so far, to study the effect of various substituents on thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid on complex equilibria. In an earlier paper⁴, we reported the formation constants of thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid (TCA) with some bivalent transition metal ions and discussed the thermodynamic parameters. The present paper reports an investigation aimed at the complexation equilibria between 2-X-TCA (X=propyl, phenyl or 2'-furyl) and Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) or Zn(II) in aqueous medium. The effect of ionic strength, dielectric constants as well as thermodynamic parameters such as ΔG° , ΔH° , ΔS° accompanying complex formation have been discussed. The electrostatic and cratic components have been determined to get an insight of the nature of bonding in these complexes.

Experimental

The ligands were prepared⁵ by condensing L-cysteine and appropriate aldehyde and repeatedly recrystallised to get pure samples. The purity was checked by elemental analysis, ir and melting points. Details of materials, apparatus and pH titration technique were the same as reported earlier⁴. Following solutions (total vol 50 ml) were titrated against standard potassium hydroxide in nitrogen atmosphere: (i) HNO₃ (4.0 × 10⁻³ M); (ii) HNO₃ (4.0 × 10⁻³ M) + ligand (2.0 × 10⁻³ M); (iii) HNO₃ (4.0 × 10⁻³ M) + ligand (2.0 × 10⁻³ M) + metal nitrate (4.0 × 10⁻⁴ M).

Values of \bar{n}_d , \bar{n} and pL were calculated from Irving and Rossotti formulae⁶. All the three ligands form 1:1 and 1:2 complexes with all metal ions studied except Mn(II) which forms only 1:1 complex. The 2-phenyl TCA-Cu(II) system could not be studied because of its precipitation. The log K_a values were computed using (i) half \bar{n} method, (ii) successive approximation and (iii) least squares method. The values agree closely and hence the formation constants calculated by the least squares method are reported (Table 1). The standard deviation⁶ was ±0.05 and limit of error⁷ ±0.6.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) AND Zn(II) CHELATES AT 30°

	2-Propyl TCA		2-Phenyl TCA		2(2')-Furyl TCA	
	0.00 M	0.10 M	0.00 M	0.10 M	0.00 M	0.10 M
II ⁺	6.20	5.97	7.87	7.65	8.07	7.91
Mn(II)	2.79	2.67	3.42	3.25	3.43	3.32
Co(II)	3.10	3.01	7.45	7.30	7.79	7.62
	(2.32)	(2.21)	(6.44)	(6.29)	(6.71)	(6.56)
Ni(II)	3.74	3.61	5.37	5.18	5.72	5.58
	(2.84)	(2.72)	(4.76)	(4.60)	(5.04)	(4.88)
Cu(II)	5.59	5.46	—	—	8.25	8.09
	(4.51)	(4.40)			(7.36)	(7.20)
Zn(II)	3.06	2.90	4.98	4.84	5.43	5.26
	(2.28)	(2.16)	(4.13)	(4.02)	(4.74)	(4.63)

Figures in parenthesis indicate the values of log K_a.

Results and Discussion

The overall stability constants with respect to the metal ions follow the order Mn(II) < Co(II) < Ni(II) < Cu(II) > Zn(II). In case of 2-phenyl TCA and 2(2')-furyl TCA, the order of Co(II) and Ni(II) was reversed. Similar trends were observed by many workers^{8,9} and attributed to the additional stabilization due to Jahn-Teller distortion. The order with respect to ligands is 2-propyl TCA < 2-phenyl TCA < 2(2')-furyl TCA. The trend can be explained as follows.

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The low basic character of thiazolidine-4-carboxylic acid (pK 6.1) compared to the analogous compounds like proline (pK 10) and cysteine (pK 8.2) can be ascribed to the inductive effect of electronegative sulphur atom transmitting to iminic nitrogen. This effect is less pronounced in cysteine because the sulphur and iminic nitrogen are separated by two carbon atoms but is more pronounced in TCA where the two are separated by only one carbon atom. In 2-propyl TCA, the propyl group being less electron donating, enhances the effect of sulphur resulting in marginal decrease in pK value. The phenyl and furyl groups, in contrast, mask the inductive effect of sulphur atom thereby increasing the pK values. This is in agreement with observed low values of 5,5-dimethyl TCA (5.98)¹ and methylol TCA (5.03)¹⁰ compared to parent TCA.

Effect of ionic strength : The stability constants at different ionic strengths (0.02, 0.05 and 0.10M) at 30° reveal that $\log K_a$ gradually decreases with increasing ionic strength. This shows that the ligands are interacting with metal ions both in undissociated and dissociated forms simultaneously. The thermodynamic stability constants were obtained by extrapolating the linear plots of $\log K_a$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ to zero ionic strength (Table 1).

Effect of temperature : Titrations were performed at 25, 30, 40 and 50° at 0.10 M ionic strength to evaluate the thermodynamic parameters. The values of ΔG^\ddagger , ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger have been calculated using standard equations¹¹ and presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF 1:1 AND 1:2 METAL CHELATES AT 30° AND $\mu=0.10$ M

Metal ion	$-\Delta G^\ddagger$	$-\Delta H^\ddagger$	ΔS^\ddagger e.u.
	(Kcal mole ⁻¹)	(Kcal mole ⁻¹)	
2-Propyl TCA			
Mn(II)	3.72	3.66	0.21
Co(II)	4.20 (3.08)	3.43 (2.97)	2.50 (0.34)
Ni(II)	5.03 (3.79)	3.34 (2.79)	3.92 (2.70)
Cu(II)	7.60 (6.14)	4.80 (4.57)	9.20 (5.18)
Zn(II)	4.06 (3.10)	3.20 (3.09)	2.83 (0.03)
2-Phenyl TCA			
Mn(II)	4.34	4.53	0.63
Co(II)	8.23 (7.32)	10.18 (8.77)	6.43 (4.78)
Ni(II)	5.72 (5.49)	7.22 (6.42)	4.95 (3.06)
Zn(II)	5.49 (5.03)	6.75 (5.60)	4.15 (1.89)
2(2')-Furyl TCA			
Mn(II)	4.34	4.63	0.95
Co(II)	7.55 (7.09)	10.63 (9.18)	10.16 (6.18)
Ni(II)	6.40 (5.72)	7.78 (6.81)	5.38 (3.60)
Cu(II)	7.78 (7.09)	11.29 (10.04)	11.58 (9.73)
Zn(II)	5.72 (5.49)	7.34 (6.46)	5.34 (3.20)

Values in parenthesis indicate the values of $\log K_a$.

The order of increase in ΔS^\ddagger values is the same as that of formation constants. The positive ΔS^\ddagger values reveal that entropy is favourable for complex formation. That these reactions are exothermic and spontaneous in nature is evidenced by negative values of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger , respectively. To get an insight of the nature of bonding of these complexes, ΔG^\ddagger and ΔH^\ddagger are separated into their electrostatic (ΔG_e^\ddagger and ΔH_e^\ddagger) and non-electrostatic or cratic (ΔG_c^\ddagger and ΔH_c^\ddagger) components as suggested by Degischer and Nancollas¹².

The values of ΔG_c^\ddagger are significantly more negative than ΔG_e^\ddagger indicating the non-electrostatic forces being stronger than the electrostatic forces in 1:1 chelates. The difference in the electrostatic and cratic components decreases in the order Cu(II) > Ni(II) > Co(II) > Mn(II) which indicates that ionic character increases with increasing number of unpaired electrons in the reverse order Cu(II) < Ni(II) < Co(II) < Mn(II). The values for 1:2 equilibria indicate a marked decrease in the ionic character of the complexes and indicate that metal-ligand bonds in the *bis*-complexes are more covalent than those in corresponding mono-complexes. As suggested by Tingpol and Nancollas¹³, ΔG^\ddagger values for 1:1 chelates are more negative than 1:2 chelates indicating that mono-complexes are energetically favoured over *bis*-complexes.

The thermodynamic ligand field stabilization energy (δH) calculated for the complexes under study

TABLE 3—ELECTROSTATIC AND CRATIC COMPONENTS OF THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

	Electrostatic		Cratic	
	$-\Delta G_e^\ddagger$	ΔH_e^\ddagger	$-\Delta G_c^\ddagger$	$-\Delta H_c^\ddagger$
2-Propyl TCA				
Mn(II)	1.80	0.69	4.35	4.35
Co(II)	2.30 (1.83)	0.88 (0.70)	4.33 (3.68)	4.31 (3.67)
Ni(II)	2.61 (2.35)	1.00 (0.90)	4.85 (3.87)	4.86 (3.87)
Cu(II)	3.77 (2.89)	1.44 (1.11)	6.26 (5.68)	6.24 (5.68)
Zn(II)	2.37 (1.76)	0.91 (0.67)	4.12 (3.77)	4.11 (3.76)
2-Phenyl TCA				
Mn(II)	1.89	0.72	5.07	5.06
Co(II)	3.16 (2.80)	1.21 (1.07)	9.45 (8.40)	9.44 (8.39)
Ni(II)	2.84 (2.43)	1.09 (0.93)	6.81 (6.43)	6.81 (6.42)
Zn(II)	2.66 (2.13)	1.02 (0.83)	6.53 (5.86)	6.51 (5.86)
2(2')-Furyl TCA				
Mn(II)	1.96	0.75	5.10	5.09
Co(II)	3.98 (3.11)	1.53 (1.19)	9.08 (8.50)	9.06 (8.28)
Ni(II)	2.91 (2.54)	1.11 (0.97)	7.30 (6.70)	7.31 (8.06)
Cu(II)	4.29 (3.88)	1.64 (1.49)	9.43 (8.59)	9.42 (8.58)
Zn(II)	2.92 (2.40)	1.12 (0.94)	6.85 (6.49)	6.84 (6.43)

Figures in parenthesis indicate the values of $\log K_a$.

TABLE 4—STABILITY CONSTANTS AT DIFFERENT WATER-ETHANOL MEDIUM AT 0.10 M AND 30°

Ethanol Mole fraction	10%	20%	30%	50% (v/v)
2-Propyl TCA				
H ⁺	6.09	6.23	6.35	6.58
Mn(II)	2.79	2.93	3.04	3.25
Co(II)	3.11 (2.33)	3.25 (2.45)	3.40 (2.59)	3.62 (2.80)
Ni(II)	3.70 (2.84)	3.81 (2.94)	3.94 (3.07)	4.13 (3.30)
Cu(II)	5.57 (4.49)	5.70 (4.61)	5.84 (4.16)	6.08 (5.05)
Zn(II)	2.98 (2.72)	3.10 (2.41)	3.24 (2.55)	3.46 (2.74)
2-Phenyl TCA				
H ⁺	7.74	7.86	7.97	8.21
Mn(II)	3.38	3.54	3.70	3.96
Co(II)	7.42 (6.41)	7.58 (6.54)	7.74 (6.68)	7.93 (6.89)
Ni(II)	5.34 (4.71)	5.47 (4.85)	5.62 (5.03)	5.90 (5.34)
Zn(II)	4.97 (4.13)	5.08 (4.28)	5.21 (4.42)	5.44 (4.67)
2(2')-Furyl TCA				
H ⁺	8.03	8.16	8.32	8.57
Mn(II)	3.40	3.51	3.64	3.88
Co(II)	7.73 (6.65)	7.87 (6.77)	8.02 (6.92)	8.23 (7.15)
Ni(II)	5.70 (4.97)	5.84 (5.09)	5.96 (5.24)	6.22 (5.43)
Cu(II)	8.22 (7.31)	8.37 (7.44)	8.54 (7.56)	8.81 (7.85)
Zn(II)	5.37 (4.65)	5.48 (4.88)	5.61 (4.97)	5.79 (5.19)

Figures in parenthesis indicate the values of log K_s.

were found to be Co(II) 25.35, Ni(II) 36.76, Cu(II) 32.60 for 2-propyl TCA; Co(II) 35.40, Ni(II) 38.20 for 2-phenyl TCA; Co(II) 35.67, Ni(II) 38.21, Cu(II) 34.58 for 2-furyl TCA. These values confirmed that the binding sites of the complexing reagents are oxygen and nitrogen as reported in the literature for structurally similar ligands¹⁴.

Effect of dielectric constants on stabilities: A number of studies^{15,16} have been made on the dependence of equilibria on properties of solvents. On introduction of organic solvent in water the solvent characteristics gradually undergo change. In the present investigation, the stability constants were determined at 10, 20, 30 and 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium at 0.10 M ionic strength and at 30°. The equilibrium constants, pK or log K, increase with decrease in dielectric constants. The plot of these values against 1/D were non-linear while those against mole fraction exhibit linearity. Thus, the stability constants of the metal chelates are directly

dependent on the mole fraction of ethanol and not on the dielectric constant of the solvent mixtures suggesting that the predominant factor governing the dissociation equilibria is the solvating nature of the solvent. Since water solvates the metal ion to a greater extent than ethanol, the less solvated metal ion has a greater capacity to attract the ligand than the heavily solvated metal ion. This explains the increase in complexing ability of the metal ion with mole fraction of ethanol.

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